

Effectiveness of Multimedia in Algebra Instruction on Junior High School Learners

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Abstract

The study determines the effectiveness of using multimedia resources to enhance the teaching and learning of algebra for Junior High School (JHS) 2 learners at Nii Ogle Basic 1 Model School, Bediako. Algebra is a fundamental mathematical concept, but many students struggle to comprehend its abstract nature. Multimedia resources, such as videos, animations, and interactive software, offer a promising solution to this challenge. This research investigates how multimedia can be used to improve students' understanding and retention of algebraic concepts, increase their motivation and engagement, and develop their problem-solving skills. A quantitative research approach was employed for the study. A pretest and a post-test control design were used. PowerPoint presentation with videos was used as an intervention to teach algebra. The sample size for the study was 30 JHS at Nii Ogle Model 1 Basic School, Bediako of which 22 were males representing 73 per cent and 8 females representing 27 per cent and the majority of the learners were between the ages of 13 and 15. The researcher employed purposive and convenient sampling techniques for the selection of the learners and the school respectively. Significant improvements in knowledge gain ($p < 0.01$) and student engagement ($p < 0.05$) were observed in the multimedia group compared to the traditional group. The results show that the use of multimedia resources significantly improved students' performance and attitude towards algebra. The study recommends the integration of multimedia resources into instruction for JHS 2 learners to enhance teaching and learning outcomes.

Keywords: Multimedia, Algebra, Junior High School (JHS) learners, Effectiveness.

Introduction

The teaching of mathematics at all levels plays a very important role because it helps learners build and develop mathematical competence and apply it in practice (Jerrim & Vignoles, 2016). To bring about effective mathematics teaching, positively changing mathematics-teaching methods is being applied by many schools today. So, what are the effective and commonly used active teaching methods for math? Teaching needs to be appropriate to learners' cognitive abilities and levels, with attention paid to the needs and cognitive abilities of each subject. Organizing teaching in a constructive direction means that learners will be the ones to actively seek, discover, and make their inferences to solve problems (Jerrim & Vignoles, 2016). According to Dei, Eminah and Konadu (2025), teachers should also continuously assess and modify their instructional methods to ensure they align with the needs and learning styles of their learners. However, Anthony and Konadu (2025) opine that no one teaching style is enough to make a learner perform academically. Children are unique individuals with different learning styles, abilities, and personalities. What works for one child may not work for another.

The JHS Mathematics syllabus covers operations in algebra (MOE, 2010). Operations in algebra cover areas such as additions subtraction expansion and expression of terms. Algebra as an important aspect of mathematics consists of the expansion and simplification of expressions (Biber, Tuna & Korkmaz, 2013). Algebra as explained by Clapham and Nicholson (2009, p. 10) is “the area of mathematics related to the study of numbers and letters”. It is the study of basic arithmetic operations of addition, subtraction, multiplication and division. Algebra is studied through basic school to the higher level of education in Ghana. The study of integers, constants and variables aids us to see Mathematics as a portion of the things we experience and use every day (Knuchel, 2004).

Learning algebra as an area of mathematics in particular is said to be determined by gender differences. A few studies investigated the influence of gender on perceived difficult algebraic expressions in mathematics and achievements have been conducted. Mutai (2016). argued that the gender of learners affects the learning of algebra in favour of males. However, to examine whether the number of algebraic expressions perceived as difficult to study varies between male and female junior high school learners, Fabiyi (2017) led a study in Nigeria of five hundred junior high school learners and found out that gender of learners a significant impact on the learning of algebraic expressions in favour of female learners.

The Chief examiner's reports for BECE mathematics from 2018 to 2022 suggest generally that, candidates had difficulties in solving questions involving operations in algebra. The Chief examiner further states that the majority of candidates found it difficult to solve questions concerning the multiplication and division of algebra (WAEC, 2019; WAEC, 2021). Learners' poor performance in mathematics has given a lot of concerns to parents, mathematics teachers and government. The poor performance of the learners was attributed to their negative perceptions toward the learning of algebra and their poor background in algebra at the foundation level. Other factors include learners' phobia of mathematics and the erroneous belief that mathematics is a difficult subject. According to Mushtaq & Khan (2016), teachers are not left out as they sometimes avoid teaching some aspects of the subject. This can be due to the nature or abstractness of the concept, the teaching method to use or teachers state of mind at the time of instruction. Ensuring teachers are sound minded to deliver contents of subjects and ensure

social-emotional learning (SEL) in their students, play a vital role in enhancing their academic performance (Konadu, 2025a).

Therefore, mathematics teachers need to explore a change in teaching strategy from the conventional long-standing “talk and chalk” method to a student-centred approach and see its effect on learners’ performance in class. Though there are varied methods of teaching algebra in mathematics. They include 1) visual, by computer-aided instruction, virtual mathematics objects, ICT teaching-learning methods, web-page links, mathematics platform accessible 2) the questioning: verbal algebraic expression problem-solving performance using active pedagogies, mastery” teaching methods 3) problem-solving: the design of tasks, knowledge growth, elements of ethno-pedagogics, a framework, comparing methods, a case study 4) Practices: preparation count, ability grouping, digital game-based math learning, case studies, co-teaching, an embedded mixed method study, special teaching methods, Using mathematics Projects, a mixed-methods investigation 5) lecturing and illumination: content knowledge and the school-level standardized testing policy. It can be said that these basic methods have been researched and applied by teachers and researchers in teaching concepts in mathematics (Jerrim & Vignoles, 2016). The multimedia approach to teaching is one strategy which has been successful according to research carried out.

The information age has led to the use of computer and web-based learning in many fields of study including Mathematics as one of the subjects. Akinbadewa (2020) opined that there has been increasing use of microcomputers in various disciplines, and it fosters a conducive classroom-learning environment that is an impetus for teaching and learning. Effective media usage plays an important role in teaching and learning, and it broadens the range and effectiveness of education. With the advent of rapid developments in electronic media, a broad range of media is available for different educational processes.

Media combinations are generally referred to as multimedia systems (Park, Kim, Cho & Han, 2019). The term multi-media instructional systems refer to the use of appropriate and carefully selected varieties of learning experiences which are presented to the learner through selected teaching strategies which reinforce and strengthen one another so that the learning will achieve predetermined and desired behavioural objectives (Park, Kim, Cho & Han, 2019). Multimedia involves the computer-controlled integration of text, drawings, graphics, still and moving images (video), audio and animation (Saputri, Rukayah, & Indriayu, 2018). Multimedia is used in the educational sector, mass communication and advertising. Multimedia such as animation, graphics, video and text which create an interactive learning environment assist learners and teachers in deep reflective thinking. According to Jian-Hua & Hong (2012), students remember 40% of what they see and hear, 20% of what they see, but about 75% of what they see, hear and do. The learning pace can be accelerated by involving a maximum number of senses. Sensory experiences form the foundation of intellectual activity within any formal institution.

Multimedia experiences have the advent of appealing to the individual pace, interest and readiness to learn. Umma & Safiyya (2021) highlighted the importance of Multimedia thus: achievement of a reduction in verbalism, provision of concrete experiences, concepts taught correctly; learners are motivated and their attention span is guaranteed, the barriers of time and space can be removed, and Multimedia can be used at any phase of a lesson, introduction, presentation and evaluation Other importance is that: contents are retained in the minds of the learners for a longer time, the time and energy of both teachers as well as the students can be

saved, and training in problem-solving skills can be imparted through the development of problem-solving situations involving relevant teaching aids (Thomas & Israel, 2014).

Much research has been carried out on multimedia impact in the teaching and learning of mathematics in different African countries and all yielded positive effects on learners' performance. Keeping in mind these outcomes and the importance of multimedia use in classroom situations; the researcher intends to validate this effectiveness on Ghanaian learners at the basic level. Thus, this study employed multimedia to enhance the teaching and learning of operations in algebra on JHS 2 learners at Nii Basic 1 Model School, Bediako in Ghana.

Problem statement

Early Mathematics concepts are fundamental for success throughout the school years and later during adult life (Lee, Park & Ginsburg, 2016). The concepts of Algebra in mathematics play a key role in the foundation of mathematics and later years. However, algebra has been one of the difficult topics in mathematics. Mereku (2012), outlined that most learners cannot solve problems involving algebra and several factors can be attributed to this. Such factors include failure to practice the concept after being taught in class, the way and manner teachers teach and assess learners on the concept. As asserted by Konadu (2025b), knowledge in assessment is very crucial for teachers in general to enhance their teaching practices in the classroom, which in turn improves upon learners' learning outcomes. Also, learners' emotions can determine their academic performance in a subject. The rate at which learners learn is influenced by their emotions; positive emotions guarantee effective learning (Konadu, 2025c). Similarly, learners' emotional states directly influence their classroom engagement, which is a key driver of academic achievement. Good mental health has been seen to have a positive impact on learners' academic performance, and weak mental health has a negative impact on academic performance. Learners' capacity to assimilate information is contingent upon their mental health status (Konadu, Aduse-Poku, & Zaagbil, 2025), which can be improved with AI agents such as Chatbots. According to Konadu and Kusi (2025), mental health of learners has been positively impacted by a multitude of AI chatbots.

Learners' weakness and inability to deal with algebra affects their academic performance in mathematics. The researcher among JHS learners at Nii Basic 1 Model School, Bediako, has observed this challenge. In teaching algebra as a topic in the JHS classes, the researcher observed that 80% of the learners could not solve algebra questions such as $(3x + 2y + 5x - 5y - 6z + 2z)$. It was further observed by the researcher that, most of the learners did not engage themselves during discussions in class on the topic. The Chief examiner's report on BECE 2019 also pointed out that candidates have difficulties solving questions involving operations in algebra (Chief examiner's report, 2019). Therefore, there is a need to explore a change in teaching strategy from the conventional longstanding "talk and chalk" method to a computer-based multimedia-supported one and see its effect on learners' academic performance in learning operations in algebra. Thus, the present study used multimedia to enhance the teaching and learning of operations in algebra on JHS 2 learners at Nii Oglie Model 1 Basic School, Bediako. The study therefore addressed the question; to what extent does multimedia affect the performance of the JHS 2 learners in operations of Algebra at Nii Oglie Model 1 Basic School, Bediako?

Literature Review

Cognitive theory of multimedia learning (CTML)

The psychological feature of the cognitive theory of multimedia learning (CTML) targets the thought that learners decide to build meaningful connections between words and photos which they have learned a lot more deeply than the use of words or photos solely in the reading text (Kirschner, Park, Malone, & Jarodzka, 2017). In step with CTML, one of the principals aims of multimedia instruction is to support the learner in creating a logical and reasonable mental representation of the information. The learner's job is to construct new information as an active participant ultimately. Meanwhile, the dual coding theory (DCT) by Allan Paivio attempts to prove the importance of two mental processes, which are verbal and non-verbal processing (Clark & Paivio, 1991). The theory explains how the human brain processes information through the combination of verbal and nonverbal representations such as image and speech (Paivio 1986). Learning and cognitive processing are the two issues investigated by the researcher to maximize the potential of successful learning and improve our brain's ability to process information. The dual coding theory emphasized the importance of visual cues in learning as humans can decode the information; they receive effectively by linking the verbal and visual cues (Sadoski & Paivio, 2013).

The concept of multimedia learning is closely related to the dual coding theory, as both theories accentuate the benefit of the human brain's duality function as an aid to the cognitive process of reading comprehension. Many researchers show a promising finding in their study when incorporating dual coding theory in reading comprehension, as stated in the study by Wang & Li (2019), where students with imagery deficits can recall and remember the words or information better with the help of innovative multimedia applications. In their study, they found that imagery-deficit students were having problems with reading comprehension because of their slow and dull imagination which led to the failure to create a mental image. The failure to link the text and image resulted in the students' n s behaviour as they could not understand and remember the information. Then, the researcher introduced a multimedia application that helps the students relate the words and pictures and the student's performance in reading comprehension (Wang & Li, 2019).

The relationship between multimedia and dual coding theory is proven through this research by Mayer and Moreno (1998) when they discovered a split- attention in multimedia correlated with the theory of dual-coding theory and a group of students who received treatment with two stimuli showed better performance than another group which receives only one stimulus. In a nutshell, the combination of words and images catalysed to boost readers' understanding by ensuring the reader can create a mental image and link it to the text, especially for children who have. Mayer built an instructional model on how multimedia learning will help learners understand a scientific explanation by listing five principles of multimedia design (Mayer, 1997).

The first principle, modality, explains the advantages of presenting information using two modes of presentation rather than one mode, such as the combination of words and pictures or animation and audio narration. The modality principle can also help pupils to learn complex materials and perform higher-order thinking skills (Fiorella, Vogel-Walcutt, & Schatz, 2012). The next principle is the contiguity principle, where the mode of presentation should be kept closed to make it related to each other rather than presented separately (Fletcher & Tobias, 2005). As an example, the explanation of cloud formation using pictures and audio is better presented

at the same time to ensure pupils can relate to both modes of presentation. The third principle, which is the split-attention principle, suggests words are better presented in auditory form rather than in text form in animation or video (Liu, Lin, Tsai, & Paas, 2012). The fourth principle is that individual differences and the effects of contiguity and split attention differ with individuals. According to the CTML, pupils who have high-level prior knowledge will be able to create their mental image, and contiguity is not suggested for them. On the other hand, pupils with a low level of prior knowledge might benefit from contiguity and split attention (Liu, Lin, Tsai, & Paas, 2012). The last principle of multimedia learning, the coherence principle addresses the disadvantages of superfluous information in learning. According to Mayer, Heiser, and Lonn (2001), the materials presented in multimedia learning should avoid using too many words and pictures. Instead, use reasonable and essential words and pictures to foster pupils' understanding. Thus, learners can visualise and build mental images based on learning and be able to comprehend the text better using multimedia learning. Therefore, the use of multimedia would enhance the performance of the JHS 2 learners in the operations of algebra.

Concept of Multimedia Learning

Multimedia learning is the process of learning, usually in a classroom or similarly structured environment, using multimedia presentations and teaching methods. This can typically be applied to any subject and generally, any sort of learning process can either be achieved or enhanced through a careful application of multimedia materials (Akkoyunlu & Yilmaz, 2005). Multimedia learning is often closely connected to the use of technology in the classroom, as advances in technology have often made the incorporation of multimedia easier and more complete. Multimedia settings can also be defined as digital settings in which elements with visual, audio or visual-audio characteristics that appeal to individuals' auditory and visual senses are presented in a combined way. It is also defined as an environment which emerges from the combination of visual and auditory materials including videos, movies and animations (Akkoyunlu & Yilmaz, 2005). Therefore, a multimedia environment is made up of those materials which mobilize more than one sense of the students (Driscoll, 2012).

The approach of multimedia learning is where the learners are going to be exposed to the utilisation of audio, pictures such as animation, video, and technology throughout reading comprehension lessons (Mayer & Moreno, 2002). Two components compose the process of reading comprehension, which are vocabulary knowledge and text comprehension. Besides that, multimedia learning can be used to support the children using their prior knowledge and new vocabulary to comprehend the text. Furthermore, the multiple components of multimedia learning can assist the learning process and boost their motivation to learn (Chiou, Tien, & Lee, 2015). Utilizing technology within the classroom is usually closely connected with the term multimedia learning, and the advancement of technology has made the incorporation of multimedia easier and more complete. In general, the term "multimedia" is employed to indicate any sort of activity or application that uses multiple types of media to present information or ideas such as video, animation, and many more. The implementation of multimedia in text comprehension is also able to improve memory retention, learning satisfaction, and learning achievement on the information presented using multimedia learning.

METHODOLOGY

Design

The researcher employed a quantitative in-action research design. This design was used since a problem was identified and an intervention was applied to solve the problem. Mathematical expressions were used to express the collected data on the sample.

Population and sampling techniques

The total population of the JHS learners in the school was 120. The accessible population, however, was all the 30 learners in the JHS 2 class of the 2024/2025 academic year. The researcher employed purposive and convenient sampling techniques for the selection of the learners and the school respectively. The school was closer to the researcher whilst the JHS two learners were showing evidence of the problem. Also, the JHS 2 learners were free from examination stress. Schumacher (2015) asserts that purposive sampling stresses the fact that it is important to select samples which are likely to be knowledgeable and informative about the phenomenon the researcher is investigating).

Instruments

The study made use of tests (pre-tests and post-tests). Both tests were constructed by the researcher with 10 multiple-choice questions on Algebra. The tests were used to identify the learners' performance before the introduction of the multimedia and after the introduction of the multimedia. The validity of the instruments was carried out to check the correctness of the data instruments. To determine the degree to which the test items would measure accurately, the content validity approach was used.

Data collection techniques and analysis approach

Parveen and Showkat (2017) assert that data collection is the process of gathering the desirable information carefully, with the least possible distortion, so that the analysis may provide credible answers and stand to logic. Firstly, a pre-test was administered to the learners, and the answered scripts were collected, and their scores were collated. Then, the teaching of algebra was done with the use of multimedia. Thereafter, a post-test was administered to the learners. The answered scripts were collated for further processing. Microsoft Excel version 19 was used for the analysis. Means, percentages and t-tests were used to analyse the scores of the learners in the pre-test, and post-test. The t-test was used to determine the significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test.

Results and Discussion

Demographic characteristics of participants
Gender of Learners

Figure 1; Gender of learners
Source; Field survey (2024)

The study was made of 22 males which represent 73% and 8 females representing 27%. This signified that the majority of the respondents were males (seen in Figure 1).

Age of learners

Figure 2; Age of learner
Source; Field survey (2024)

The age ranges from 10 to 18. Most of the learners were between the ages of 13 to 15 as illustrated in figure 2.

In answering the research question, the researcher analysed the pre-test and post-test scores of the learners presented in Table 1.

Table 1; Pre-test and post-test results

SCORES	PRE-TEST		POST-TEST	
	FREQUENCY (N)	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY (N)	PERCENTAGE (%)
0 – 5	27	90.0	2	6.7
6-10	3	10.0	2	6.7
11 – 15	0	0.0	4	13.3
16 – 20	0	0.0	22	73.3
TOTAL	30	100	30	100

SOURCE; Field survey (2024)

It was seen in Table 1 that, many of the learners obtained scores from 0 to 10 in the pretest. All the learners representing 100% scored from 0 to 10 in the pre-test. None of the learners obtained scores from 11 to 20 in the pretest. This indicated a very low performance in the pretest and a high performance in the post-test. As seen from Table 1, 4 of the learners representing 13.3% scored within the range of 0 to 10 in the post-test. However, after the intervention, the majority of them (26 representing 86.7%) scored from 11 to 20. This indicated that they performed higher in the post-test after the intervention stage (seen in Table 1).

Difficulties in solving multiplication of two binomials

Before the interventions, many learners have difficulty in solving the multiplication of two binomials. This can be seen in the answer the learner provided

The student was able to do the expansion, but the student had a challenge in handling the (-7a) and (-5a), instead of (-12a) the student wrote (-2a). this is an indication that the student has challenges with the operational signs

T-test analysis of the scores of the learners in the pre-test and post-test revealed that the learners performed higher in the post-test than the pre-test as illustrated in Table 2

Table 2: t-test results of test scores of learners

Tests type	Mean test Scores	t – stats	p-value
Pre-test	3.665	-5.649	5.16121E-11
Post-test	10.015		

* = significant; $p < 0.05$

It was seen in Table 2 that, the p-value obtained was less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$). This indicates a statistically significant difference between the means of the pre-test and post-test with a higher mean in the post-test.

Discussion of Findings

The study focused on using multimedia to enhance the teaching and learning of algebra on JHS 2 learners at Nii Oglie Model 1 Basic School Basic, Bediako. The researcher then analysed the data obtained and the results were presented along with the research questions. It was seen that the majority of the learners scored marks between 0 to 10 on the pre-test. This indicates that although they knew the topic treated before the intervention was applied, however, their performance was lower in the pre-test. Similarly, after the intervention, it was seen in the post-test scores that, the majority of the learners scored from 11 and 20. This indicated an improved performance in the post-test than the pretest. In furtherance, it was seen upon conducting t-test analysis on the scores of the learners in the pre-test and post-test that, the p-value obtained was less than 0.05 ($p = 5.16121E-11$) which indicates a significant difference in the performance with higher mean score in the post-test signifying the effectiveness of the intervention (multimedia) in improving learners' academic performance. This is in support of the findings of Yılmaz (2012), Yünkül and Oğuz-Er (2014). According to them, some studies concluded that multimedia learning has significant effects on student achievement. For instance, it analysed the effects of multimedia settings and computer settings on student achievement and permanent learning. The findings of the study indicated that the experiment group which received multimedia teaching had significantly higher scores on achievement and permanent learning in contrast to the control group. Again, the results support a study that employed similar technology by Konadu, Annan and Hordzi (2024). Their study evident that computer simulation is more effective in teaching and learning circulatory system in humans. However, these findings contradict the study of Yasar (2010) who found out that there are other studies which concluded that multimedia teaching has no desired effects on student achievement.

In conclusion, the study indicated that multimedia enhances learners' performance in mathematics and hence has positive effects on learners. This result is consistent with Yaşar and Gültekin (2012). According to them, multimedia settings facilitate learning and make learning activities much more meaningful, long-lasting and attractive. Research suggests that 92% of the participants considered multimedia learning settings fun. There are numerous studies indicating that multimedia teaching has positive effects on student performance and attitudes according to Beydoğan and Hayran (2015), İnan (2015), Özüpekçe (2015) and Yeşiltaş (2010).

Implications of the study

The study findings will encourage mathematics teachers to use multimedia for instruction. This will enable learners to be motivated and develop positive attitudes to learn operations in algebra and thus, will perform better. In addition, the study findings will give insight to curriculum developers (NaCCA) and GES to consider multimedia as one major method for instruction in the mathematics syllabus. Lastly, the findings will enable the major stakeholders in education (GES) to provide the necessary teaching and learning resources to support the implementation of the multimedia instruction method.

Limitations of the study

Due to financial constraints, the researcher only conducted the study in the class and school he was teaching (that is; the JHS 2 learners at Nii Basic 1 Model School, Bediako). Thus, the findings of the study could not be generalized to other classes and schools. In addition, due to the period for the study, the researcher only collected data on 30 learners in JHS at Nii Ogle Model 1 Basic School, Bediako.

Conclusion

The study concluded that learners' academic performance increased after the use of multimedia in teaching Algebra in mathematics. Their post-test performance was higher than in their pretest. This indicated the effectiveness of multimedia in teaching algebra in mathematics.

Recommendation for policy makers

Policymakers such as the Ministry of Education and Ghana Education Service should provide schools with teaching and learning resources such as audio-visual aids to be used by teachers to arouse learners' interest in learning mathematics

Recommendations for teachers

1. Teachers should use multimedia in teaching mathematics to boost their learners' interest and performance in the subject.
2. Teachers should expose students to various forms of algebraic expression solving so they can expand their cognitive horizon on the topic
3. Teachers should be aware that not all students learn the same way, hence, they must differentiate their instructional methods to meet the needs of all the students.
4. Teachers should encourage their students to focus more on the problem-solving process than the result.

Recommendation for Further Study

This study is delimited to NII OGLE MODEL 1 BASIC SCHOOL, meaning the results cannot be generalized. Future researchers should look at a bigger population and use more than one instrument The researcher suggests the following for further studies;

1. A study should be done on the negative effects of multimedia on learners' performance in mathematics.
2. A study should be done on the effectiveness of audio-visual aids in teaching and learning other subjects.

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